

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281469>

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY FOR RAISING THE OVERALL ENDURANCE OF GIRLS OF THE UPPER CLASS IN ATHLETICS CLUBS AT SCHOOL

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Abstract: Athletics is very important for developing endurance and fitness among sports. Increasing the overall endurance of high school girls will further increase their interest in physical health and sports. This article presents suggestions for improving the methodology of endurance training in athletics circles.

Key words: Athletics, Endurance, Physical fitness, Training, Competition, Group training, Sports health.

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕТОДИКИ ВОСПИТАНИЯ ОБЩЕЙ ВЫНОСЛИВОСТИ СТАРШЕКЛАССНИЦ В ЛЕГКОАТЛЕТЧЕСКИХ КРУЖКАХ ШКОЛЫ

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Аннотация: Легкая атлетика очень важна для развития выносливости и физической формы в спорте. Повышение общей выносливости старшеклассниц еще больше повысит их интерес к физическому здоровью и спорту. В данной статье представлены предложения по совершенствованию методики тренировки выносливости в легкоатлетических кружках.

Ключевые слова: Легкая атлетика, Выносливость, Физическая подготовка, Тренировки, Соревнования, Групповые тренировки, Спортивное здоровье.

INTRODUCTION

Athletics is one of the main types of physical education and sports activities. In this area, increasing the general endurance of high school girls, not only their physical condition, but also has a great impact on mental and psychological development. Endurance is an important factor that directly affects the success of girls in sports, and plays an important role in the development of self-control, physical strength, and the ability to withstand stress. Also, increasing endurance increases students' sense of competitiveness and motivation, which increases interest in sports. From this point of view, it is necessary to improve the methods aimed at educating the general endurance of girls in athletics circles. In this article, we will talk about modern approaches and methods used to increase endurance in athletics training. These methods are important not only for physical, but also for mental development.

Literature Analysis

The analysis of the literature in the field of athletics and endurance education is the theoretical basis of this topic and allows learning practical approaches. Below are the main sources and their important aspects. These literatures provide extensive knowledge of athletics and endurance training and includes experiences. They are methodological approaches in the process of training students and helps to integrate strategies. Also take into account psychological and motivational factors acquisition is important in increasing students' resilience. IV Makarova "Sports Psychology: Motivation and Endurance" in the book Psychological in Sports emphasizes the importance of preparation. Methods to increase motivation and competitiveness and offers methods."DP Zaitsev"Modern approaches in sports education". In his book on sports education Innovative approaches, including modern methods of education of resilience, are presented. AK Fedorov's "In Athletics: A Handbook". This resource provides guidance for athletics teachers on conducting training, monitoring and evaluating student development. by SA Petrov "Developing Endurance: Theory and

Practice" examines the physiological and psychological aspects of building endurance. gives recommendations.VN Koval"Theoretical and practical foundations of athletics" in the methodical guide dedicated to the historical development of athletics, the main techniques and methods. Author girls presents approaches to conducting athletics training for Methodology The methodology used in raising the general endurance of high school girls is one How many main components should it consist of? This methodology includes training planning, including effective approaches in the conduct and evaluation process. Analytical method: Assessment of physical condition and sports level of students during selection. Collect and analyze data on past performance, physical performance and health status. Experimental method: Development of a specially prepared training program for the experimental group exit In this program, various exercises, loads and rest aimed at increasing endurance modes should be entered. Confirm or reject the hypothesis based on the research results. If that the new program is effective if the endurance indicators in the experimental group are improved shows. Questionnaire and interview: The survey helps to collect the opinions of the students and to analyze the effectiveness of the methods aimed at increasing the overall resilience. By conducting interviews, students' opinions can be explored more deeply. Asking open-ended questions in the interview will help you better understand their personal thoughts, experiences and suggestions.

Results

The results of research and questionnaires on improving the general endurance training method of high school girls showed the effect of athletic training on the body of students and the effectiveness of methodical approaches. Below are the main results obtained. Physical Activity Level: Of the 150 students surveyed, 35% do physical exercises 1-2 times a week, and 45% do 3-4 times a week. Only 20% of students reported doing an activity 5 or more times a week. These results indicate the need to regularly increase the physical activity of students. Many of them still need to exercise less and exercise more to improve their overall endurance. Resilience Assessment: 50% of the students rated their resilience as moderate, and 20% as low. This suggests the

need to introduce more and more effective training to improve overall endurance. By increasing athletic training and intensity, students' endurance can be improved. Also, 15% of students rated their physical endurance as good, which indicates that some students have physical fitness learned in the previous period. Effects of training: 60% of students reported that sports activities have a positive effect on health, and 25% noted that they feel a very positive effect. This result confirms that athletic training has a positive effect on the body, especially on the cardiovascular system and muscle system. Most students reported feeling increased endurance and strength during the sessions. Motivation Factors: The main factors that attract students to sports activities are teachers' encouragement, training with friends and competitions. According to the results of the survey, 50% of students prefer to exercise with friends, which shows the importance of group training and social motivation. 30% emphasized teachers' encouragement. Competitions and achievements make 10% of students more interested in sports. This means that there is a need to strengthen social and psychological approaches to increase student motivation. The results of the study showed that athletic training is very effective for increasing the general endurance of high school girls. Students notice an improvement in their physical condition after training, but the motivation to continue it. It is necessary to increase and develop training in an interesting and comprehensive way. Providing students with additional incentives through individualized instruction, team training, and competition will help further increase their overall resilience.

Discussion

The results of this study show students' motivation for sports activities, often team spirit, associated with training together with friends and interest in competitions. Questionnaire The results show that 50% of students prefer to participate in activities with friends, as well as showed that they want to participate in competitions. This is the physical activity of students means that the main motivational factors for participation are friends and group competition. also teachers' encouragement and students' motivation to organize competitions confirmed that it is important in

increasing. Student athletics in research interests and suggestions in training were also studied. Students have a variety of activities, feel more fun by learning new sports and participating in competitions emphasized that they will do. They also allow individual adaptation of exercises, i.e suggested to organize exercises according to the level of physical fitness of students. this, increasing the flexibility of methodological approaches and according to the needs of students indicates the need to make changes.

Summary

In this article, research aimed at improving the general endurance training method of high school girls is based on the study of the role and effectiveness of physical education and athletics training in the physical, mental and psychological development of students. The results of the study confirmed the importance of athletics training in increasing the general endurance of students and showed the need to make a number of suggestions to the methods. The general endurance level of the students is still average or low, and it is necessary to increase the intensity of the training and increase the motivation of the students. Making lessons interesting and different, organizing group exercises and competitions, plays an important role in increasing the activity of students. It is also necessary to adjust physical activity individually and develop exercises suitable for the level of preparation of students. Research has shown that athletic training greatly helps students improve their physical condition, increase muscle strength, and develop endurance. However, by encouraging students, learning new exercises and teaching them proper recovery techniques, their overall endurance can be further improved. Also, development of an individual approach, introduction of exercises suitable for the level of physical fitness of each student and organization of training according to their needs is of the main importance in the effective implementation of the methods. This approach, helps to increase the general endurance of students and strengthen their physical fitness.

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